

PHILOSOPHICAL ANTHROPOLOGY: A NON-REDUCTIVE PHYSICALISM
ALTERNATIVE TO DUALISM AND HOLISTIC DUALISM

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Introduction

The aspects of body, mind, and soul are of immense interest for philosophers, scientists, ethicists, and policymakers. If the humans are composed of two distinct aspects or substances—body and soul—how do they exist together as one person, and how does the body relate to the soul? In order to explain the mystery of human anthropology, numerous explanations are given in philosophical, theological, and scientific disciplines. Some of the prominent positions include dualism, holism, holistic dualism, and non-reductive physicalism.¹ Historically, the philosophers believed in the dual nature of body and soul. Similarly, ecumenical Christian tradition affirmed that humans are composed of body and soul. However, the traditional views of philosophical dualism and theological holistic dualism are challenged by many modern philosophers, religious thinkers, and scientists.²

In this paper, the nonreductive physicalist position of anthropology is argued. Nonreductive physicalism argues that there is no soul in human beings and the higher capacities of humans—morality, reasoning, and spirituality—are explainable as brain functions. Non-reductive physicalists deny dualism but uphold meaning, responsibility, and freedom of humanity.³ First, the dominant positions of dualism, holism, and holistic dualism are discussed and evaluated. Then, arguments for nonreductive physicalism are explored, and counterarguments are analyzed. At last, the ethical and policy-making implications of nonreductive physicalism are discussed.

¹ John W. Cooper, “The Current Body-Soul Debate: A Case for Dualistic Holism.” *SBJT* 13, no. 2 (Sum 2009), 32-33.

² Cooper, “The Current Body-Soul Debate,” 32.

³ Nancey C. Murphy, *In Search of the Soul: Four Views of the Mind-Body Problem*, ed. by Joel B Green and Stuart L Palmer (Downers Grove, Ill: InterVarsity Press, 2005), 115–118.

Philosophical Dualism

Philosophical dualism has its original roots in the myths of “Orphism.”⁴ Some of the prominent variants of philosophical dualism include Platonic dualism, Aristotelian hylomorphism, and Cartesian mind-body dualism.

Orphic Myths

Greek philosophy for the most part taught the dualistic nature of humans. Pythagoreans restructured the “Orphic” myths of dualism and influenced next-generation dualists. According to them, the soul could be purified from bodily impurities by three paths—the ascetic, the aesthetic, and the intellectual. The intellectual path is the highest pathway to purify the soul, as it helps to rationalize the soul. When the soul associates with pure reason, it gains the capacity to escape from the body and return to a higher heavenly realm where pure mathematical reason dwells. Heraclitus mentioned that our life begins when we die, and our soul is dead in us when we are physically alive.⁵

Platonic Dualism

Plato developed his version of dualism on the foundations of “Orphic” myths and Greek philosophers. He also formulated a reminiscence theory in which he argues that human beings have immortal rational souls and possess innate knowledge before their birth. Plato taught radical dualism. Humans are composed of a soul of the higher, divine, and rational realm, and a body of the lower and mortal sphere. He elevated the status of the soul and mentioned that the soul possesses the attributes of divinity, immortality, uniformity, intellectuality, and

⁴ Derwyn Randolph Grier Owen, *Body and Soul, A Study on the Christian View of Man* (Philadelphia: Westminster Press, 1956), 34–36.

⁵ Owen, *Body and Soul*, 38–39.

indissolubility, and unchangeability. He attributed mortality, lack of intellectuality, multiformity, dissolubility, and changeability to the body and undermined its status.⁶

The soul is considered as pure reason. It needs to be escaped from the evil and corrupted body and world, as they are hindrances to the soul. The desires of the body must be suppressed in order to enjoy the benefits of the soul. He mentioned that the soul is infected with the evils of the body. The body is the source of infinite troubles, ailments, lusts, worries, fantasies, and quarrels. He argues that the purified soul returns to the divine and heavenly realm from which it came. After death, the soul will be absorbed into the universal reason. The pathway to this unification is the purification of the soul through intellectual pursuit and acquisition of knowledge. Therefore, the origin and destiny of the soul is pure reason, and it finds its true existence only in a disembodied state.⁷

Aristotelian Dualism

Aristotle is one of the greatest philosophers of all time, and he is also a student of Plato. Aristotle proposed a hylomorphic analysis of the body in which the body is subject and matter, the soul is the form, and the natural living body is a composite of matter and form. The account of the soul consists of the first stage of actualization and a stage of the essence. He presented a form of dualism in which the matter is potentiality, and the form is actualization.⁸ Aristotle attempted to avoid the dualism of two substances and proposed that man is a unified substance of form and matter of the same substance. However, he returns to a metaphysical dualism as he states that pure form is pure reason unmixed with the matter; therefore, it is divine

⁶ Owen, *Body and Soul*, 38–41.

⁷ Owen, *Body and Soul*, 41–43.

⁸ Fred D. Miller, "Aristotle's Philosophy of Soul," *The Review of Metaphysics* 53, no. 2 (1999), 310-312.

and eternal. Therefore, reason in human beings is a divine element and a spark of universal “pure reason.” When man pursues knowledge, he can escape from the matter and eventually unite with “pure reason.”⁹

Cartesian Dualism

The arguments of Descartes consist of methodic doubt, the primacy of mind, and mind-body dualism. Descartes employed a methodic doubt to know about the certainty of the realities. It is also known as metaphysical or hyperbolic doubt. He attempted to doubt everything that is uncertain. All the sensory experience must be doubted because it makes errors. However, he could not doubt a few things, including his mind, mathematical formulas, and God. He argued for the primacy of the mind and gave a notion of mind-body dualism. He argued that the mind (soul) is a non-extending and thinking thing. On the other hand, the body is an extended and non-thinking thing.¹⁰

Cartesian dualism divides the properties into mental capacities and physical materials. Hence, there are two basic types of substances with distinct natures—unextended thinking substance (soul) and unthinking and extended substance (body). Descartes argued that man is essentially a thinking being, i.e., a soul. Although body and soul are distinct from each other, they are causally related. He also stresses that the body is not essential for the existence of a person. Man can exist without having a body.¹¹

⁹ Owen, *Body and Soul*, 41–43.

¹⁰ René Descartes, *Meditations on First Philosophy: With Selections from the Objections and Replies* tr. J. Cottingham, Ed. (Cambridge University Press, 1996): 7-16, 35, 54.

¹¹ Kevin Corcoran, *Soul, Body, and Survival: Essays on the Metaphysics of Human Persons* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2001), 2–3.

Holism

Holists argue that the Bible presents the human person as a totality, a whole, a unitary being.¹² Anthony Hoekema argues that the Bible does not teach any strong antithesis between body and soul. Since God created everything good, the body is not evil according to scriptures.¹³ The holists reject both dichotomy and trichotomy, as they do not accurately represent the biblical idea of humanity. One of their arguments is that the terms “dichotomy” and “trichotomy” are objectionable because they suggest that humans can be divided into parts.¹⁴ They argue that the Bible is not interested in explaining the composition of human beings; rather, it provides information on how humans are related to God. The Bible is not interested in the psychological or anthropological constitution of man. J. A. T. Robinson argues that any part of the human being can be represented as a “whole” of a human being at any time.¹⁵

Holists argue that the Hebrew word “*nephesh*” (soul) refers to the whole person and connotes the totality of human nature, not necessarily representing an idea of the immaterial component. Similarly, the word “*ruach*” (spirit) refers to an animating spirit that is the seat of emotion and organ of mental acts, and it overlaps with the word “*nephesh*.” In any case, it should not be considered as a separable aspect of humans; rather, it refers to the whole person from a certain standpoint. They deduce that the worldview of the Old Testament was always the wholeness of a person and there was no hint of dichotomy or trichotomy.¹⁶ Similarly, the Greek words “*psyche*” (equivalent to the Hebrew word “*nephesh*”) and “*pneuma*” (equivalent to

¹² Anthony A. Hoekema, *Created in God's Image* (Carlisle, UK: Paternoster Press, 1994), 210.

¹³ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 206.

¹⁴ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 209–210.

¹⁵ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 204, 210.

¹⁶ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 210–213.

Hebrew word “*ruach*”) in the New Testament often refer to the whole man to represent the fullness of life in distinction from the physicality of life.¹⁷

Interestingly, although holists argue for the wholeness of humanity, some of them recognize the two sides of humanity—physicality and non-physicality. They see two complementary aspects of man and consider them to be a mysterious unity. They prefer to identify the man as a psychosomatic unity in order to stress the unity and justify the two sides of humanity.¹⁸ In spite of their arguments for unity, they agree that man still exists in an intermediate state (a period between death and resurrection) without a physical body. They argue that the Bible does not teach anything significant about the anthropological description of life in an intermediate state; rather, it whispers about it. This state is incomplete and provisional and anticipates a future resurrection of the body.¹⁹

The practical implications of a holistic approach include the church being expected to have a concern for the whole person, not limiting their services to only one aspect, either soul or body; it also demands a comprehensive approach to missions and service; it also affects the way schools prioritize their instruction; and it maintains a balanced approach to family life and encourages the expansion of medical, scientific, and psychological disciplines.²⁰

Holistic Dualism

Holistic dualism refers to a theological position of human anthropology that affirms that God created humans as unified persons of body and soul, and the soul exists in an

¹⁷ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 213–215.

¹⁸ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 217–218.

¹⁹ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 221–222.

²⁰ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 222–225.

intermediate state between death and resurrection. The term "holistic dualism" captures the idea of the unity of body and soul and allows the possibility of the personal existence of a human being without a physical body. There are two kinds of holistic dualism advocated by traditional Christian theologians. The term "substance dualism" states that the soul and body are distinct substances that are united to form a whole human being. This view is maintained by Augustine, Anselm, Eastern Orthodox tradition, Calvin, many Protestant theologians, and contemporary Christian philosophers. The term "soul-matter dualism" states that humans possess a substantial soul, which informs matter to comprise a bodily human form. Therefore, a human being is not a composition of two substances but one being consisting of a spiritual soul and matter. This position was originally proposed by Thomas Aquinas; therefore, it is also called "Thomistic dualism." Most Roman Catholics, some traditional Protestants, and some contemporary Christian philosophers adhere to this position. All dualists support that body and soul are distinct and the soul can survive apart from the body.²¹ The proponents of holistic dualism lay out the arguments of ecumenical tradition and scriptural data. The rise of scientism, followed by the denial of objectivity, universal ethics, and religion, resulted in the marginalization of the traditional worldviews in academic institutions. In order to meet this challenge, philosophers and theologians reformulated anthropology and accommodated the modern views of human anthropology.²²

²¹ Cooper, "The Current Body-Soul Debate," 32–34.

²² James Porter Moreland and Scott B Rae, *Body & Soul: Human Nature & the Crisis in Ethics* (Downers Grove, Ill: InterVarsity Press, 2000), 7.

Holistic Dualism in Ecumenical Tradition

Early church fathers like Clement of Alexandria, Origen, and Augustine upheld the view of *holistic dualism*. Although they believed in the distinct substance of humanity, they refused to undermine the role of the body. They refused the gnostic dualism and taught the goodness of the physical universe and humanity as they were created by God. They upheld the resurrection of the physical body. They grounded their human anthropology in the biblical doctrine of creation and resurrection of the body.²³ Some of the early church fathers, including Clement of Alexandria, Origen, and Gregory of Nyssa, were trichotomists. According to them, the spirit is the essential human self, and the soul is the mediator between spirit and body. Later, the dichotomy view triumphed over trichotomy and emerged as the orthodox view of the church.²⁴

Augustine of Hippo affirmed the unity of human nature and taught that humanity is the soul that operates the body. He emphasized that man is the unity of soul and body. The soul is superior to the body because it is a simple substance and immortal. Augustine's anthropology is called a two-substance dualism. According to him, the soul permeates and animates the entire body, and the body depends on the soul for its existence. Medieval scholastic philosopher Thomas Aquinas depended on Aristotle to explain the unity of human nature and insisted on the intimate correlation of soul and body. However, he also maintained that the soul is distinct from the body and it survives physical death. The Protestant reformer John Calvin agreed with the Augustinian Platonism. Calvin defended the intermediate state and affirmed the conscious fellowship with Christ.²⁵

²³ Owen, *Body and Soul*, 52–54.

²⁴ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 8–9.

²⁵ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 10–12.

Holistic Dualism in Scriptures

The scriptural data of the creation of humanity, death experience, intermediate state, and the hope of resurrection, and the relationship between brain and mind support the arguments of holistic dualism. First, the creation account gives the necessary clues to understand the two origins and dual aspects of humanity. God created man in his image to reflect his glory and exercise his dominion on the earth (Gen 1:26-27). When God created man, He created him as an embodied person. God fashioned man into a bodily form (*basar*) out of the dust of the earth. He breathed the breath of life (*neshama*) into his nostrils, and man became a living being (Gen 2:7). The breath (*neshama*) is also considered as the wind or spirit (*ruah*), which is an immaterial aspect. Hence, the origin of man involves two separate sources—the earthly component of the dust of the earth and the heavenly component of the breath of life.²⁶ Now, it is evident that man has a visible material body according to scripture and common sense. However, scripture also teaches that man is also dependent on another life-giving force “the breath of life” for his survival (Job 42:7, 34:14-15). Man is not considered as a living “soul” (*nepes*) until the material body receives the breath of life from God. Peter Gentry argued that —“the soul” is the joining of material and immaterial aspects and it refers to the wholeness of man as an animated body with the life of God according to the Old Testament.²⁷ Although the words “soul” (Heb. *Nephesh* and Gk. *psyche*) and “spirit” (Heb. *ruach* and Gk. *pneuma*) were used interchangeably in the Bible, they help to recognize an immaterial aspect of human beings in a material body. This view of

²⁶ Peter Gentry, “Sexuality: On Being Human and Promoting Social Justice,” *Christian Psychology* 8, no. 1 (2014): 49–52.

²⁷ Gentry, “Sexuality,” 52–54.

creation is compatible with that traditional idea of death—separation of the immaterial aspect (soul or spirit) of a person from the material body (Ecc 12:7).²⁸

Second, the Bible distinguishes the immaterial and material aspects of humanity.²⁹ The depiction of death in the Bible indicates that there is a separation of material and immaterial aspects at death.³⁰ The portrayal of the existence of the dead in an intermediate state supports the idea of an immaterial soul. There is a continuity of personal identity between dead and living in the Old Testament.³¹ Similarly, in the New Testament, the dead are referred to as spirits (*pneuma*) and souls (*psyche*), and they exist in an intermediate state. In Luke 16:19-31, the parable of Lazarus and the rich man suggests an imaginative intermediate state. After the death of Lazarus and the rich man, they still existed in some realm. Lazarus went to be with Abraham in a comfortable place, and the rich man suffered torment in Hades. Although there was no resurrection at this point, there was a great separation between them.³² God's covenantal faithfulness is tied to the sustenance of his people. This implies that saints are preserved in an intermediate state.³³ There is no indication of a cessation of personhood at death and recreation at the resurrection. Instead, they are considered to be alive to God in that stage of an intermediate state. Similarly, the authors of the Bible asserted the hope of resurrection and indicated the continuity of personhood after life (1 Thess. 4:13-18, 2 Cor. 5:1-10, Philip. 1:21-24, 1 Pet. 3:19-20, Heb. 12:23, and Rev. 6:9-11).³⁴

²⁸ Wayne A. Grudem, *Systematic Theology: An Introduction to Biblical Doctrine* (Leicester, England: InterVarsity Press, 1994), 473–475.

²⁹ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 117.

³⁰ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 114.

³¹ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 68–69.

³² Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 124–125.

³³ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 120.

³⁴ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 112–15, 145–148, 151.

Evaluation of the Arguments

Philosophical dualism emphasizes the ontological distinction between body and soul (or spirit/mind) for the most part. According to Cartesian dualism, the mind is a distinct substance from the body. The physical body is of the lower realm of earth, and it is evil and mortal. On the other hand, the soul is the essence of humanity, and it is of the higher heavenly realm and immortal. In order to be delivered from the body, the soul must be purified by intellectual pursuit and suppression of the body. After death, the purified souls will be unified to the pure reason of heaven. Similarly, Christian tradition argues for the biblical notion of the immaterial and material aspects of humanity. God created a good material universe, and he blessed it. God created man in his image in an embodied form without sin (Gen 1:31). The idea of bodily resurrection in the Bible rejects the notion of philosophical dualism (1 Cor 15:35-58).³⁵ In Matthew 10:28, there is a distinction between body (*soma*) and soul (*psyche*), and the physical death of a material body is distinct from the eternal punishment of the soul.³⁶ Hence, theological dualism is distinct from philosophical dualism.

The holists argue that the human person is a totality, a whole, a unitary being.³⁷ They argue that there is no antithesis between body and soul. Since God created everything good, the body is not evil.³⁸ Interestingly, the holists distinguish the physicality and non-physicality of humanity and stress a psychosomatic unity.³⁹ They argue that the Bible does not teach anything significant about the anthropological description of life in the intermediate state; rather, it

³⁵ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 49–54.

³⁶ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 117.

³⁷ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 210.

³⁸ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 206.

³⁹ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 217–218.

whispers about it.⁴⁰ In contrary to the holists' arguments, the experience of death indicates that there is a separation of material and immaterial aspects at death (Job 34:14-15, Eccl. 12:7).⁴¹ The portrayal of the existence of the dead in the intermediate state supports the idea of the immaterial soul. There is a continuity of personal identity between dead and living in the Bible. In Luke 23:42-43, Jesus promised to one of the thieves that he will be in paradise with Jesus on the very same day. The Lord's promise implies that they still exist as the same persons in paradise (an intermediate state) before their resurrection. If there was no intermediate state of souls, it does not make any sense in this promise.⁴²

Some Christian philosophers argue that traditional holistic dualism undermines the Christian orthopraxis. They argue that the body-soul distinction promotes intellectualism and adversely influences missions and service. Some theologians argue that the idea of holistic dualism entails the Platonic concept of the immortal soul. The notion of the existence of the soul after death and its non-earthly nature has its roots in Greek philosophy. However, the Christian understanding of the soul is distinct from the Platonic and Greek philosophy of the soul with inherent immortality. According to Christian dualists, God sustains the soul after physical death by his power and endows it with a glorified body in the resurrection. The body is not inherently evil. The Christian view of holistic dualism and immortality of the soul is distinct from the Platonic view of the immortal soul.⁴³ However, the proponents of traditional holistic dualism argue that there is no correlation between body-soul distinction and dichotomies of nature-grace and intellectualism-quietism, etc., Theological dualism does not necessarily contribute to the

⁴⁰ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 221–222.

⁴¹ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 114.

⁴² Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 127–128.

⁴³ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 196–198.

religious, functional, and social dualism. Cooper stated that it is absolutely possible to believe in the intermediate state and value the current life as embodied humans for the glory of God. However, liberation theologians express their concern over social justice and argue that holistic dualism undermines human responsibility.⁴⁴ On the other hand, the physicalists deny the possibility of immaterial minds on the grounds of mental causation and consciousness. They argue that immaterial minds are not capable of developing causal relations with physical objects and with other immaterial minds.⁴⁵ They suggest that mental causation and phenomenal consciousness are not physically reduced.⁴⁶

Non-Reductive Physicalism

Physicalism is primarily a denial of dualism. However, physicalism is distinct from materialism in that it does not necessarily entail disbelief in the existence of God and non-material beings. The non-reductive part of physicalism does not invalidate meaning, responsibility, and freedom of humanity. Although physicalism is a kind of monism, it specifies the substance to be physical in nature. Non-reductive physicalists believe that there is no soul in human beings. The higher capacities of humans—morality, rationality, and spirituality—are explainable as brain functions. They also argue that the moral responsibility of human beings is compatible with physicalism.⁴⁷ Human morality and responsibility depend on sophisticated symbolic language. It requires a sense of self, capacity to pursue aspirations, and the capacity to evaluate actions.⁴⁸ Nancy Murphy summarizes the teaching of physicalism as follows:

⁴⁴ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 180–182, 190.

⁴⁵ Jaegwon Kim, *Physicalism, or Something Near Enough* (Princeton University Press, 2005), 2–3.

⁴⁶ Kim, *Physicalism*, 1.

⁴⁷ Murphy, *In Search of the Soul*, 115–118.

⁴⁸ Murphy, *In Search of the Soul*, 125.

“...We are our bodies— there is no additional metaphysical element such as a mind, soul, or spirit. But, second, this “physicalist” position need not deny that we are intelligent, moral, and spiritual. We are, at our best, complex physical organisms, imbued with the legacy of thousands of years of culture, and, most importantly, blown by the Breath of God’s spirit; we are *Spirited bodies*.”⁴⁹

The physicalists argue that our distinctiveness as humans is not necessarily dependent on the ontological substance “soul”; rather, we need to recognize our humble origins as another species of mammals.⁵⁰ The complex functioning of our organisms needs to be attributed to the complex organizational capacity rather than attributing it to an immaterial substance, “soul.”⁵¹ The only difference between higher and lower animals is the alignment of consciousness in higher animals. However, Nancy admits that it is a hard problem for neuroscientists to explain how consciousness develops from the brain.⁵² Although physicalists deny the presence of a rational soul, they differ on reductionism. A reductive view denies that humans are truly rational, moral, and religious because they do not have a soul. However, a non-reductive view insists that the higher capacities of humans, like rationality, morality, and religiosity, can be explained as brain functions and associated with human social relationships, cultural factors, and our relationship with God.⁵³

Modern science sheds new light on human thoughts, sensations, emotions, and their association with chemical and electrical stimulation of the brain. The dependence of the mind on the physical brain seemed to deny the possibility of an immaterial component (soul) in the human body.⁵⁴ They argue that humans are closely related to animals according to science and

⁴⁹ Nancey C. Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies? Current Issues in Theology* (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2006), ix.

⁵⁰ Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies*, 55.

⁵¹ Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies*, 57.

⁵² Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies*, 59-60.

⁵³ Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies*, 70.

⁵⁴ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 206–209.

scriptural data. Physicalists express their concern about the imbalanced approach to biology and neurosciences from the Christian theologians. They deny that the Bible does not give evidence for the existence of an ontological immaterial substance, “soul.” According to them, the Bible primarily talks about humanity’s relationship with God, rather than providing ontological human anthropology.⁵⁵ They argue that our identity as humans is found in self-conscious relationality and embodied formative histories of ourselves according to scriptures and neurosciences. Our personhood is inseparably bound up in our physicality and tied to the created cosmos and life experiences and relationships. Therefore, no personhood survives the experience of death. Although Christian physicalists believe in the resurrection of the body, they argue that our personhood is preserved in God’s own being after death, and we receive a gift of resurrection from God himself.⁵⁶

Counterarguments to Non-Reductive Physicalism

Non-reductive physicalists argue that there is no soul in human beings and the higher capacities of humans, like morality, rationality, and spirituality, are explainable as brain functions. Nancy admits that it is a hard problem for neuroscientists to explain how consciousness develops from the brain.⁵⁷ In contrast to the physicalist view, there was no strong empirical evidence for the correlation between mental events and brain events. The occurrences of the brain are dependent on the mental activities of a person. The opponents of non-reductive physicalism stress that evidence certainly does not favor the physicalist view of the brain and

⁵⁵ Joel B. Green, *Body, Soul, and Human Life: The Nature of Humanity in the Bible. Studies in Theological Interpretation* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2008), 70–71.

⁵⁶ Green, *Body, Soul, and Human Life*, 178–180.

⁵⁷ Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies*, 60.

mind.⁵⁸ Some theologians critiqued Christian physicalists for moving away from the traditional doctrines by compromising with modern scientism and naturalism.⁵⁹ The complex relation of cognitive functions with the brain is not fully established. However, it does not grant that the philosophical and theological expressions of an immaterial soul in human beings are legitimate conclusions. The ethical frameworks and social policies cannot be based on dogmatics, without rational explanations or scientific grounding.

Similarly, other reductive physicalists argue that mental causation and phenomenal consciousness can be conditionally physically reduced. The mental and intentional properties of acts of faith, intention, and perception are functionally characterizable and reducible.⁶⁰ Though reductive physicalism offers a novel perspective, it is not empirically established, and it has connotations to materialism. Some of the cognitive capacities and qualia cannot be reduced to the physical domain.⁶¹ Hence, the nonreductive physicalism serves as the viable and reliable model for human anthropology and ethical consideration.

Implications for Ethics and Social Policy

Philosophical anthropology is extremely important for developing ethics and social policy. The accurate representation of humanity has a profound impact on politics, government, and policy-making priorities. The notions of philosophical dualism penetrated the law and social policy.⁶² The ecumenical tradition neglected the physical life by upholding the notions of

⁵⁸ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 206–209.

⁵⁹ R. Keith Loftin and Joshua R. Farris, “Introduction,” in *Christian Physicalism: Philosophical Theological Criticisms*, ed. R. Keith Loftin and Joshua R. Farris (Lanham, MD: Lexington Books, 2017), xv.

⁶⁰ Kim, *Physicalism*, 5.

⁶¹ Kim, *Physicalism*, 5–6.

⁶² Elizabeth S. Anker, *Fictions of Dignity: Embodying Human Rights in World Literature* (United States: Cornell University Press, 2012), 17-18.

immaterial soul, resurrection, and afterlife. The underprivileged communities in the church believed in glory in the afterlife while suffering slavery and mistreatment in the colonial era. Similarly, the marginalized people suffer social suppression and economic disadvantage in the capitalistic world with the hope that justice will be provided. Solid evidence-based philosophy is essential to ground the important calls for social justice, human rights, civil rights, and accurate allocation of resources to all people.

The arguments of body-soul and body-mind relationships help the larger discussions of gender norms, reproductive arguments, faith and science, ethics in artificial intelligence use, and bioethics. The critics point out that the American law and policy sometimes rely on an incomplete picture of humanity and expressive individualism instead of the lived experience of embodiment.⁶³ O. Carter Snead discussed the importance of valuing the vulnerable, providing information to patients, and ethical considerations in clinical trials and vaccine testing.⁶⁴ The violation of minimal care, omission of safety procedures, and deliberate experiments on unborn children and vulnerable point out the loopholes in the system and need for reforms in bioethics on the grounds of dignity of humans.⁶⁵ The sociological cognizance and scientific assessment of humanity are essential in understanding what is needed for people and developing appropriate policies needed for the time.

⁶³ O. Carter Snead, *What It Means to Be Human: The Case for the Body in Public Bioethics* (United Kingdom: Harvard University Press, 2020), 5.

⁶⁴Snead, *What It Means to Be Human*, 19–21.

⁶⁵Snead, *What It Means to Be Human*, 33–34., 36

Conclusion

Philosophical anthropology uses the terms “body,” “mind,” “soul,” and “spirit” to explain the human embodiment. The philosophers, religious leaders, and political thinkers differ in explaining who human beings are at the core of their existence. The philosophical dualism affirms the two distinct substances, body and soul; it considers the material aspect of the body to be evil or of a lower level. The ecumenical Christian tradition affirms holistic dualism, which depicts a unified person of material body and immaterial soul, and resurrection; this traditional view of holistic dualism has been challenged by modern philosophers. The philosophical arguments of dualism and religious notions of resurrection and afterlife are not proven scientifically with the empirical evidence. Nonreductive physicalists argue cognitive and mental capacities of humans—morality, reasoning, and spirituality—are explainable as brain functions. They reject the immaterial aspect of soul or spirit in humans. Despite the rejection of the immaterial soul, they uphold meaning, responsibility, and freedom of humanity.⁶⁶ The nonreductive physicalism model is reliable for explaining human anthropology, as it is grounded in sound reasoning and scientific explanation. It also upholds the foundational aspects of human dignity, inherent value, and individual rights that are tied to ethics and policy making.

⁶⁶ Cooper, “The Current Body-Soul Debate,” 32–33 and Moreland and Rae, *Body & Soul*, 7–8.

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